

6

5

4

3

2

1

Ø 156.00

Ø 241.80

Ø 273.00

Ø 187.20

Top View
Scale 1:7.5

Isometric View
Scale 1:7.5

Front View
Scale 1:7.5

SECTION B-B
SCALE 1 : 7.5

Right Side View
Scale 1:7.5

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:
DIMENSIONS ARE IN MILLIMETERS
SURFACE FINISH:
TOLERANCES:
LINEAR:
ANGULAR:

FINISH:

DEBURR AND
BREAK SHARP
EDGES

NOT SCALE DRAWING

REVISION

All the dimensions are in mm.

	NAME	SIGNATURE	DATE		
DRAWN	Ayan				
CHK'D					
APP'VD					
MFG					
Q.A				MATERIAL:	
				WEIGHT:	

TITLE:
**WheelAssembly
(with Hub)**

DWG NO.
Right_wheel

A4

SCALE:1:10

SHEET 1 OF 1

6

5

4

3

2

1

D

D

C

C

B

B

A

A